

GULAYAN SA BAKURAN PROGRAM IN APLAYA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL-ANNEX, SANTA ROSA CITY: BASIS FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the reconfiguration of the annual activities of the Department of Education (DepEd) in response to the public health emergency brought by COVID-19, specifically focusing on the 2020 Brigada Eskwela and Oplan Balik Eskwela as clarified in DepEd Order No. 53, s. 2020. The research employs a qualitative design, utilizing interviews and document analysis to explore the adaptation strategies of DepEd in ensuring the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and personnel while supporting the provision of learning opportunities through multiple delivery modalities. One significant initiative, Gulayan sa Tahanan (Urban Vegetable Gardening at Home), is highlighted as part of the Brigada Eskwela and School-Family-Community Partnership. This program promotes sustainable food supply at homes, engaging learners in gardening activities that enhance their understanding of Science, Home Economics, Health, and other learning areas, while raising awareness about the importance of health and food security. Additionally, Gulayan sa Tahanan fosters economic productivity by teaching entrepreneurial skills, as learners and families can sell excess produce to generate income. The analysis reveals that the initiative not only addresses food security but also minimizes household expenses and provides a practical model for small-scale food production, thereby contributing to family and community resilience during the COVID-19 crisis. Overall, the study underscores the multifaceted benefits of integrating urban gardening into educational activities, highlighting its role in promoting health, education, and economic stability in times of crisis.

Keywords: *Brigada Eskwela 1, Gulayan sa Tahanan 2, Health and Safety in Education 3, Sustainable food supply 4, urban gardening in education 5, Covid-19 6*

INTRODUCTION

The Aplaya National High School-Annex, as one of the schools in the Division of Santa Rosa City, has actively participated in the implementation of the "Gulayan sa Bakuran Program," as mandated by Division Memorandum 330, s.2020, titled "Implementation of Gulayan sa Bakuran Project." This initiative emphasizes that "Gulayan sa Bakuran: Container and Backyard Vegetable Gardening" is a productive activity for teaching and non-teaching personnel, learners, and their families. Its primary aim is to advocate for and aid in expanding food adequacy levels during the pandemic. The project is designed to achieve three objectives: developing health awareness through gardening during the coronavirus pandemic, encouraging personnel, school heads, teachers, students, and their families to plant vegetables for food consumption, and fostering an appreciation for gardening and its importance to daily life.

Despite the project's intentions, there was a lack of clarity in the guidelines provided, leading Aplaya National High School to adapt the implementation by modifying the "Gulayan sa Paaralan" procedures to fit the context of home environments. This adaptation involved activities such as vegetable gardening, utilization of garden produce, and the creation of seed banks or nurseries. This initiative aims to extend learning tasks for students and teachers while instilling the value of gardening. Over time, the "Gulayan sa Bakuran" program can help students learn from the process of growing and caring for plants.

The vegetable gardening activities initially conducted at school are now practiced at home through the "Gulayan sa Bakuran" or "Tahanan" as part of the Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) subject. During the pandemic, students, teachers, administrators, and non-teaching staff used their backyards, empty lots, or small pots to plant vegetables and fruits, providing a source of food supply during this time of crisis. Additionally, gardening has served as a productive and enjoyable leisure activity.

The researchers of this study are directly involved in the program as educators, specifically implementing the "Gulayan sa Bakuran: Container and Backyard Vegetables Gardening Program" as TLE teachers at Aplaya National High School-Annex in the City Schools Division of Santa Rosa. They have observed that the program is timely, given its objective of advocating for and aiding in the expansion of home and community food adequacy levels during the pandemic.

The project begins with an online launch and orientation after being cascaded by SDO personnel and school heads to the focal persons, teachers, and parents. After the launch and orientation, participants prepare their land or garden and seedlings for planting at home. The project's success is ensured through strong monitoring and evaluation of its implementation.

Teachers, students, parents, and non-teaching personnel are encouraged to plant easily grown vegetables at home, such as onions, sweet potatoes, ginger, garlic, radish, cassava, river water spinach, jute leaves, mustard, snow cabbage, malabar spinach,

camote leaves, gabi, tomatoes, eggplants, lady's fingers, bitter gourd, and chili peppers. These vegetables provide fresh, edible portions of herbaceous plants—roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits, or seeds—that participants can use for food consumption. Sufficient knowledge about plant growth is necessary for successful gardening. For root crops, a wide area with full sunlight and well-drained soil is essential, along with organic fertilizer and proper soil preparation. Leafy vegetables require moist, nutrient-rich soil with continuous irrigation, while fruits need fertile, sandy loam soil. Moreover, the "Gulayan sa Tahanan" program not only teaches learners how to plant and gain profit from gardening but also fosters young entrepreneurship, benefiting students from all socioeconomic backgrounds by nurturing unconventional talents and skills. This entrepreneurial activity creates opportunities, ensures social justice, instills confidence, and stimulates the economy, creating income opportunities for the participants and others.

Given these observations, the researchers believe there is a need to assess the "Gulayan sa Bakuran" program at Aplaya National High School-Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City, as a basis for an entrepreneurial program. This assessment will involve the participating teaching and non-teaching personnel and students, aiming to initiate vegetable gardens in their homes as a sustainable food basket for daily vegetable consumption.

Research Questions

The study aims to assess the Gulayan sa Bakuran in Aplaya National High School - Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City: Basis for Entrepreneurial Program

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Teaching/ Non-Teaching
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 - 1.1.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.1.4 Length of Service
 - 1.2. Students
 - 1.2.1 Age
 - 1.2.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Parents
 - 1.3.1 Age
 - 1.3.2 Sex
 - 1.3.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.3.4 Employment Status
2. What do respondents grow in their backyard in terms of:
 - 2.1 Root Crops
 - 2.2 Leafy Vegetable
 - 2.3 Fruits
3. How do plants grow in terms of:
 - 3.1 Root crops
 - 3.2 Leafy Vegetables
 - 3.3 Fruits

4. How do the respondents consume the backyard produce in terms of:
 - 4.1 Root crops
 - 4.2 Leafy Vegetables
 - 4.3 Fruits
 5. What marketing plan may be developed as Basis for Entrepreneurial Program based on the findings?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive-quantitative research. This assumed that phenomena should be studied objectively with the goal of obtaining single truth, or at least reality within known probabilities, with an emphasis on measurement, numerical data and experiments. Specifically, this study made use of the descriptive method of research with the questionnaire as the primary instrument. A descriptive research involved collecting data to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the status of the subject of the study. A descriptive study determines and reports the way things are. Descriptive research is scientific research that describes events, phenomena or fact systematically dealing with a certain area or population. Specifically, it will use a descriptive-survey research design in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population (Creswell, 2002).

In this study, the use of descriptive-survey research was employed in Aplaya National High School -Annex in the Division of Santa Rosa City for SY 2020-2021. The focus of this research was to assess the Gulayan sa Bakuran in Aplaya National High School -Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City as the basis for entrepreneurial program.

Participants of the Study

This study covered the teachers and non-teaching staff and parents and students involved in the implementation of the Gulayan sa Bakuran program. For the students, a stratified random sampling technique was used in the study since the researcher selected randomly from strata that divide the population covering Grade 7. The respondents were selected using the sampling technique so that the researcher may fairly generalize the results back to the population from which they were chosen. A total of 61 teaching staff of Aplaya National High School - Annex participated in the Gulayan sa Bakuran based on the school record. Further, all the 10 non-teaching staff were also included.

Table 1

Distribution of student participants by Section in Grade 7

Sections	Students	
	Population	Sample
Archimedes	56	10
Aristotle	56	10
Copernicus	55	10
Euclid	56	10
Kepler	56	10
Pasteur	55	10
Faraday	69	15
Descartes	72	15
Newton	66	12
Kelvin	72	15
Galileo	74	15
Pascal	71	15
Maxwell	72	15
Edison	71	15
Mendel	72	15
Ptolemy	73	14
Total	1,046	206

Table 1 shows the distribution of student participants in Grade 7 in terms of their respective sections. Using Slovin’s formula with 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, the total population of 1,046 students who were involved in Gulayan sa Bakuran had a sample size of 206. The online distance learning sections Archimedes, Aristotle, Copernicus, Euclid, Kepler, and Pasteur had 10 participants each while the modular distance learning sections had 15 student-respondents for each except for Newton with 12 and Ptolemy 14 student-participants. As stated, the sample size employed a stratified random sampling technique so that it will enable the researcher to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied and making sure that each subgroup of interest was represented.

Instrumentation

The key instrument used in the study is a survey questionnaire. A questionnaire is a set of orderly arranged questions, carefully prepared to answer the specific problems of the study (Zulueta and Costales, 2003).

A questionnaire was devised to obtain necessary data in the Gulayan sa Bakuran in Aplaya National High School -Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City as Basis for Entrepreneurial Program. It was composed of two parts. The first part determined the demographic characteristics of the respondents while the second part identified the assessment of Gulayan sa Bakuran program in Aplaya National High School -Annex in the Division of Santa Rosa City specifically asking for the grown plants classified under root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits. Further, questions pertaining to the consumption

of the produce were included. A five-point rating scale indicated below was used to answer specific questions relative to the treatise.

Rating		Range		Interpretation
5	-	4.51-5.00	-	Always (Daily/Everyday)
4	-	3.51-4.50	-	Often (4 times a week)
3	-	2.51-3.50	-	Sometimes(2times a week)
2	-	1.51-2.50	-	Seldom (Once a week)
1	-	1.00-1.50	-	Never (Never)

The draft of the instrument was submitted to the research adviser for checking. Then, it was subjected to a dry run for validation among 10 teaching and non-teaching, and 10 students and 10 parents who were not involved in the study. The results of the dry run served as a basis in revising and improving the instrument prior to its actual administration.

The instrument was administered among the respondents via online using Google forms and/or email. The gathered data were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed accordingly.

Data Gathering Procedure

The gathering of data began with the process of seeking permission and approval to conduct the study. A letter was sent to the principal or school head of Aplaya National High School Annex requesting for the approval to conduct the online survey. Upon approval, the researcher started the study by subjecting the respondents to answer the validated questionnaire. Also, questions regarding the survey were entertained and answered by the researcher and the instructions were clearly explained before the respondents started doing the activity. The last step of data gathering was collecting the accomplished survey in the google form to come up with the data that were subjected to statistical treatment, analysis, interpretation and presentation.

In addition, the ethical guidelines as specified in the research management guidelines of the Department of Education were followed by the researcher, as those ethical considerations were carefully observed throughout this study. The consent form to the participants required the researcher to explain to them the importance/significance and objectives of the study. The data and information gathered were kept in full confidentiality. The works of researchers of other authors were properly recognized.

Rating		Range		Interpretation
5	-	4.51-5.00	-	Always (Daily/Everyday)
4	-	3.51-4.50	-	Often (4 times a week)
3	-	2.51-3.50	-	Sometimes(2times a week)
2	-	1.51-2.50	-	Seldom (Once a week)
1	-	1.00-1.50	-	Never (Never)

Moreover, One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to test the significant difference on the Gulayan sa Bakuran in Aplaya National High School - Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City as Basis for Entrepreneurial Program.

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

$$MST = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k (T_i^2/n_i) - G^2/n}{k - 1}$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} Y_{ij}^2 - \sum_{i=1}^k (T_i^2/n_i)}{n - k}$$

In the given formula, F is the variance ratio for the overall test, MST is the mean square due to groups (between groups), MSE is the mean square due to error (within groups, residual mean square), Y_{ij} is an observation, T_i is a group total, G is the grand total of all observations, n_i is the number in group i and n is the total number of observations.

Pearson r Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine the significant relationships namely: how the respondents grow the plant and consumed the produce in terms of Root crops, Leafy Vegetables, and Fruits; and the respondents' profile and the plants they grow in terms of root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

In the given formula, Pearson r was used to analyze if a relationship exists between two variables, x and y . If there is a relationship that exists, then the extent that x influences y can be determined by means of the coefficient of determination which is equal to the square of r and multiplied by 100%.

r is the correlation coefficient, x_i are the values of the x -variable in a sample, $\bar{x}$ is the mean of the values of the x -variable while $y_{\{i\}}$ are the values of the y -variable in a sample and $\bar{y}$ is mean of the values of the y -variable.

Scope and Limitations

The study focuses on the assessment of the Gulayan sa Bakuran in Aplaya National High School -Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City: Basis for Entrepreneurial Program in Aplaya National High School Annex in the Division of Santa Rosa City for School Year 2020-2021. It covers the teachers, students and non-teaching staff involved in the implementation of the said program root crops such as Onions, Sweet Potatoes, Ginger, Garlic, Radish and Cassava, in leafy vegetables, River water/spinach, Jute leaves, Mustard, Snow Cabbage, Malabar Spinach, Camote leaves, and Gabi, and fruits are Tomato, Eggplant, Lady's fingers, Bitter gourd, and Chili Peppers, since the researcher will randomly select Grades 7 because the researcher is a grade 7 teacher in TLE that's why she uses grade 7 as one of her respondents.. Using Slovin's formula with 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error a total of 198 students will be selected from 16 sections. The respondents will be selected using the sampling technique so that the researcher may fairly generalize the results back to the population from which they were chosen. The school is selected because it is one of the institutions in the city division classified as very large in terms of its typology. In addition, it is the researcher's teaching post. Relative to teacher-participants, demographic profiles such as age and gender will be considered. All the 51 teachers of Aplaya National High School Annex participating in the Gulayan sa Bakuran will be involved in the study. Further, all the 10 non-teaching staff will also be included.

RESULTS

A. How Respondents Grow Specific Plants. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of root crops based on the computed F-value of 7.49.

On the other hand, leafy vegetables obtained a computed F-value 0.74 revealing that there is no significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of leafy vegetables.

Lastly, a computed F-value of 0.53 was found in terms of fruits which implied there is no significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of fruits.

B. How Respondents Consume the Produce of Specific Plants. The results disclosed that in root crops there is a computed F-value of which means that there is a significant difference on how the respondents consume the produce of specific plants in terms of root crops.

Moreover, leafy vegetables obtained a computed F-value of 8.48 explaining that there is a significant difference on how the respondents consume the produce of specific plants in terms of leafy vegetables.

Furthermore, a computed F-value of 9.94 was obtained in terms of fruits displaying that there is a significant difference on how the respondents consume the produce of specific plants in terms of fruits.

C. Relationship Between Teaching/Non-Teaching and How they Grow the Plant and Consume the Produce of a Specific Plant. A computed r-value of 7.63 was obtained interpreted as very high implying that there is a significant relationship between teaching and non-teaching personnel's manner of growing plant and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under root crops.

There is a significant relationship between teaching and non-teaching personnel's manner of growing plants and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under leafy vegetables as revealed by the computed r-value of 8.48 interpreted as very high.

Lastly, a computed r-value of 9.94 interpreted as very high was obtained displaying that there is a significant relationship between teaching and non-teaching personnel's manner of growing plants and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under fruits.

D. Relationship Between Parents/Students and How they Grow the Plant and Consume the Produce of Specific Plants. There is a significant relationship between parents and students' way of growing plants and consumption of the produce with the specified plants classified under root crops as exhibited with the obtained computed r-value of 7.49 interpreted as very high.

A computed r-value of 0.74 was garnered and interpreted as high revealing that there is no significant relationship between parents and students' manner of growing of plant and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under leafy vegetables.

Lastly, a computed r-value of 0.53 interpreted as moderate was found exhibiting that there is no significant relationship between parents and students' manner of growing of plant and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under fruits.

E. Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Teaching/ Non-Teaching Respondents. In terms of age, a computed r-value of -0.09, 0.04 and -0.05 were obtained having a negligible correlation. Thus, there is no significant relationship between age and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to teaching and non-teaching respondents.

Relative to sex, a computed r-value of 0.09, 0.16 and -0.04 with a negligible correlation were garnered revealing that there is no significant relationship between sex and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to teaching and non-teaching respondents.

Meanwhile, a computed r-value of -0.25, -0.08 and -0.01 were obtained implying that there is a negligible correlation were obtained in terms of educational attainment. Hence, there is no significant relationship between educational attainment and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to teaching and non-teaching respondents.

Furthermore, a computed r-value of -0.04, 0.18 and 0.04 interpreted having a negligible correlation were found revealing that there is no significant relationship between length of service and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to teaching and non-teaching respondents.

F Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Parent Respondents. In terms of age, a computed r-value of 0.06, 0.08 and 0.01 were obtained having a negligible correlation. Thus, there is no significant relationship between age and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to parent respondents.

Relative to sex, a computed r-value of 0.05, 0.05 and 0.12 with a negligible correlation were garnered revealing that there is no significant relationship between sex and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to parent respondents.

Meanwhile, a computed r-value of -0.09, -0.09 and -0.13 interpreted having a negligible correlation were obtained in terms of educational attainment. Hence, there is no significant relationship between educational attainment and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables and fruits to parent and student respondents.

Furthermore, a computed r-value of -0.08, -0.07 and -0.10 interpreted with a negligible correlation were found revealing that there is no significant relationship between employment status and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables and fruits to parent and student respondents.

G. Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Student Respondents. A computed r-value of -0.06, -0.02 and 0.01 were obtained having a negligible correlation. Thus, there is no significant relationship between age and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits.

Lastly, a computed r-value of -0.10, -0.09 and -0.01 interpreted having a negligible correlation were found uncovering that there is no significant relationship between sex and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to student respondents.

DISCUSSION**Table 1****Demographic Profile of Teaching/ Non-Teaching Participants**

Characteristics	F	%
1.1. <u>Age</u>		
21-30	11	18%
31-40	25	41%
41-50	19	31%
51-60	5	8%
61 and above	1	2 %
Total	61	100%
1.2. <u>Sex</u>		
Male	11	18%
Female	50	82%
Total	61	100%
1.3. <u>Educational Attainment</u>		
Bachelor's degree	37	61%
Bachelors with MA Units	17	28%
Master of Arts degree	4	6%
Master of Arts with Doctorate Units	2	3%
Doctoral degree	1	2%
Total	61	100%

1.4. Length of Service		
3 years and below	18	30%
4-9 years	24	39%
10-14 years	8	13%
15-20 years	7	11%
21 years and above	4	7%
Total	61	100%

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the teaching and non-teaching participants in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service. In terms of age, 25 (41%) of the respondents belong to 31-40 years old, 19 (31%) of the respondents belong to 41-50 years old, 11 (18%) of the respondents were from 21-30 years old, 5(8%) from 51-60 years old and 1 (2%) belong to 61 and above. The teaching and non-teaching personnel belonged to the early and middle adulthood stage with age groups spanning from 18-40 as early adults; 40-65 as middle adults. The study assumes that age variable influences the respondent's assessment of the Gulayan sa Bakuran Program as found in several studies like Scott et. al. (2020) which examined relationships between home gardening and older adults' self-reported well-being. It showed adults aged 60 and above showed positive aging-self perceptions towards aging while engaged in gardening activities at home. Gardens provide important restorative benefits for older adults. Likewise, the study of Chamin-Pui et. al. (2021) found significant associations between improvements in well-being, perceived stress, and physical activity across ages. The participants in the said study were gardeners and non-gardeners above 18 years.

Relative to sex, 50 (82%) were female and 11 (18%) were male. Majority of the teaching and non-teaching were female. The sex variable is assumed to have effect on the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program. The study of Philpott et. al (2020) revealed that gender influenced plants' richness and composition. Specifically, women plant more plant species than men. It was also concluded that plant selection as well as the richness of plants grown are likely a function of gardener socio-demographic characteristics. The findings of the said study could shed light to the present study since there is a dominance of the female group among the teaching and non-teaching personnel.

In terms of educational attainment, there were 37 (61%) respondents having bachelor's degree followed by 17 (28%) Bachelor's degree with MA Units, 4 (6%) with Master of Arts degree, 2 (3%) with Master of Arts with Doctorate Units and 1 (2%) having Doctoral degree. All the teaching and non-teaching participants were educationally qualified. Majority of them showed a basic entry requirement in the public school which is a bachelor's degree. On the other hand, it can be noted that several participants pursue continuing professional development, specifically acquiring further graduate studies units

and degrees. It indicates that teaching and non-teaching staff are already concerned about their educational qualification and professional development as revealed by Gula-gula (2021). On the other hand, there are still staff in the locale of the study whose educational qualification is equivalent to the minimum entry requirement. This could be supported by the age of the said personnel. They could acquire advanced knowledge and skills in pedagogy and work if they continue to pursue graduate studies like their fellow teachers and staff.

In terms of length of service, 18 (30%) had 3 years and below, 24 (39%) with 4-9 years, 8 (13%) having 10-14 years, 7 (11%) with 15-20 years and 4 (7%) having 21 years and above. It can be gleaned from the teaching and non-teaching personnel that they had diverse years of service in the institution. Most of them had served their school from 4 -9 years while others have been in the field for more than a decade. It signifies that they have acquired varied experiences in participating different school programs like the *Gulayan sa Bakuran*.

Significantly, among the demographic profile most of the respondents belong to 31-40 years old in terms of age. In terms of sex, majority were female and majority of the respondents' educational attainment were bachelor's degree holder. Lastly, most of the respondents had 4-9 years length of service.

Table 2
Demographic Profile of Pupil Participants

Characteristics	F	%
1.5. <u>Age</u>		
12 Years old	98	48%
13 Years old	98	48%
14 Years old	10	4%
Total	206	100%
1.6. <u>Sex</u>		
Male	110	53%
Female	96	47%
Total	206	100%

Table 2 displays the demographic profile of the student-participants highlighting age and sex. In terms of age, 98 (48%) were 12 years old, 98 (48%) were 13 years old and 10 (4%) were 14 years old. The students were at the appropriate age as Grade 7 students. Majority of them are aged 12 - 13 years old. They belong to the adolescent stage, also known as teenagers. The age characteristics of the students is assumed to influence their assessment towards the *Gulayan sa Paaralan*. According to Cornell University (2020) gardening improves opportunities for children, youth, adults, and families to gain interest and eat more fruits and vegetables. Middle school-aged students indicate that gardening affects their vegetable consumption, including improved recognition of, attitudes towards, preferences for, and willingness to taste vegetables. Gardening also increases the variety of vegetables eaten.

In terms of sex, 110 (53%) were male while 96 (47%) were female. Majority of the students were male. Van et. al. (2016) in their study found that students participating in gardening were most likely to be male of younger age and living in rural areas. It was also found that gardening was positively associated with healthy dietary habits among students such as greater fruit and vegetable consumption. Also, students also who participate in gardening report slightly lower levels of depressive symptoms and enhanced emotional well-being and experience higher family connection than students who do not participate in gardening. In the study of Lier et. al. (2016) participation in the gardening activity implemented by school is dominated by the male students. Students who participated in gardening were more likely to share frequent meals with their families than students without gardens at home. Furthermore, results showed fruit and vegetable consumption and home availability of fruits and vegetables were significantly associated with gardening activity. In general, Utter et. al. (2016) concluded that school gardens have a positive impact on student health.

The table reveals that in terms of age most of the respondents were 12 and 13 years old. Lastly, relative to sex majority of the students were male.

Table 3
Demographic Profile of Parent Participants

Characteristics	F	%
1.7. <u>Age</u>		
21-30	8	4%
31-40	106	51%
41-50	72	36%
51-60	17	8%

61 and above	3	1%
Total	206	100%

1.8.	<u>Sex</u>		
Male	28	14%	
Female	178	86%	
Total	206	100%	

1.9.	<u>Educational Attainment</u>		
1.10. Elementary graduate 2%	5		
1.11. High School graduate 50%	104		
1.12. College undergraduate 31%	63		
Bachelor's degree	34	17%	

1.13.	<u>Employment Status</u>		
1.14. Employed Specify 33%	68		
1.15. Unemployed 67%	138		
Total	206	100%	

	<u>BARANGAY/RESIDENCE</u>		
Ibaba	7	4 %	
Kanluran	4	2 %	
Labas	41	23 %	
Malusak	32	18 %	
Market Area	34	19 %	
Tagapo	60	34%	
Total	178	100%	

Table 3 reveals the demographic profile of parents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, employment status and residence. In terms of age, 8 (4%) of the respondents belong to 21-30 years old, 106 (51%) of the respondents belong to 31-40 years old, 72 (36%) of the respondents were from 41-50 years old, 17 (8%) from 51-60 years old and 3 (1%) belong to 61 and above. Like the teaching and non-teaching personnel, the parent participants belonged to the early and middle adulthood stage. It is also assumed that their age distribution influences their assessment of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program. Bui et. al. (2018) stated that parents have an impact on a child's development. The study assumes that parents also play a role in the implementation of the gardening program under study. On the other hand, Cornell University (2020) found that having a garden as an adult was positively associated with fruit and vegetable consumption.

Relative to sex, 28 (14%) were male and 178 (86%) were female. Majority of the parent participants were female. As stated in the study of Philpott et. al (2020) it revealed that gender influenced plants' richness and composition. The current study assumes that the sex variable of parents influences their assessment towards the gardening program. Specifically, women plant more plant species than men. It was also concluded that plant selection as well as the richness of plants grown are likely a function of gardener socio-demographic characteristics.

In terms of educational attainment, there were 5 (2%) who were Elementary graduates, 104 (50%) high school graduates, 63 (31%) college undergraduates and 34 (17%) obtaining bachelor's degrees. The parents showed a diverse educational level. Majority of them have completed basic education as high school graduates. Several of them have attained college level and degrees. The educational attainment of parents reflects their knowledge about planting and growing various plants. Duncan (2016) noted that households with gardens had students more interested in participating in the school garden program.

In terms of employment status, 68 (33%) were employed while 138 (67%) were unemployed. Thus, majority of the parents were unemployed. This means that they have more time to participate in the Gulayan sa Bakuran. The study also assumes that the Gulayan sa Paaralan is an avenue for the unemployed parents to generate profit to support and produce a sustainable source of food for the family. For employed parents, the gardening program assumes associations between improvements in well-being, perceived stress, and physical activity of parents as reiterated by Chamin-Pui (2021). In a systematic review on environmental influences on fruit and vegetable consumption, Cornell University (2020) revealed improved intakes in fruits and vegetables. Further, the study of Taboka (2016) showed results that gardens had positive gross margins to leafy vegetables, onions, tomatoes, and green pepper which showed higher viable gross margins.

Lastly, in terms of residence 7 (4%) reside in Ibaba, 4 (2%) from Kanluran, 41 (23%) from Labas, 32 (18%) from Malusak, 34 (19%) from Market Area and 60 (34%) residing in Tagapo. Majority of the respondents confirmed that they reside in areas near the school namely Labas, Malusak, Tagapo and Market Area. These areas are

commercial sites where there is a possibility to sell various kinds of vegetables and crops grown by the residents from the Gulayan sa Paaralan. In these areas the parents are near the market that is why they can sell their vegetables, fruits, and root crops. While in Ibaba and Kanluran they are far from the market, so they just consume it by their family. Rojo et. al. (2015) categorizes family gardens as urban food gardening which encompass agricultural activities with generally low economic dependence on material outputs. Family gardens in urban settings are non-commercial, food producing undertakings that aim to provide the respective household and families with vegetables, fruits, and herbs. The type of urban setting highly influences the character of the garden. In dense urban areas, balcony or rooftop cultivations in pots are more common, whereas in detached housing, a part of the garden is allocated to growing vegetables, fruits, and herbs.

As highlighted in this table, among the demographic profiles most of the respondents belong to 31-40 years old in terms of age. Relative to sex, majority were female and majority of the respondents' educational attainment were high school graduate. In addition, most of the parent respondents were unemployed. Lastly, most of the respondents reside in Barangay Tagapo.

Conclusions

Corollary to the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Profile of the Respondents

1.1 Teaching and Non-Teaching Personnel. Majority belong to 31-40 years old, female and having bachelor's degree. Lastly, mostly had 4-9 years length of service.

1.2 Students. Most of the respondents were 12 and 13 years old and male.

1.3 Parents. Most of the respondents belong to 31-40 years old, female and high school graduates. In addition, most of the parent respondents were unemployed and residing in Barangay Tagapo.

2. Respondents Plants Grown in the Backyard

In terms of root crops, teaching and non-teaching personnel commonly planted onions and ginger while parents and students typically were planting onions and sweet potatoes. Relative to leafy vegetables, teaching and non-teaching personnel commonly planted kamote leaves/tops and pechay while parents and students were planting kangkong and camote leaves/ tops typically.

Lastly, teaching, and non-teaching personnel usually planted sili (chili peppers) while parents and students were commonly planting tomatoes in terms of fruits.

3. How Plants Grow in the Backyard

There are varied responses on how the plants grow in the backyard. In generally, plants classified under root crops considered the following ways: in planting onions, majority of the teaching and non-teaching personnel revealed that it grows in the backyard

by transplanting/using bulbs - plants the bulb $\frac{3}{4}$ inch deep and 3 inches apart from each other while parents and students revealed that in planting onions, they ensured that the plant site receives full sunlight and maintains well-drained soil. Both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that in planting sweet potatoes, they ensure the planting site receives full sunlight and warm climate. In planting ginger, both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed they choose a planting site that receives 2 - 5 hours direct sunlight and is protected from strong winds. In planting garlic, the teaching and non-teaching personnel mentioned that they harvest garlic when most of the leaves have turned brown by digging the bulbs up while parents and students revealed that they water the plant regularly when it is dry.

Relative to radish, teaching and non-teaching personnel considered setting the planting site with partial shade from sunlight. On the other hand, parents and students considered preparing the soil, removing rocks, trash, and large sticks from the planting area. Both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that in planting sweet potatoes, they ensure the soil in the plant site is loose and not water logging.

In leafy vegetables, the following were the usual ways of growing the plants: in planting kangkong (river/water spinach), they ensure the planting site has watery or swampy and/or muddy soil with lots of organic matter and full sunlight. In planting saluyot (jute leaves), teaching and non-teaching personnel considered harvesting saluyot late in the afternoon 30 days after planting by cutting the crop 20 - 25 cm from the ground. Subsequent harvesting is done 1 to 2 weeks interval up to 7 months while parents and students revealed that they select a planting area that has full sun or partial shade with well-worked, well-drained soil rich in organic matter.

Both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that in planting mustasa, they select a planting area that has full sun or partial shade with well-worked, well-drained soil rich in organic matter. In planting pechay, teaching and non-teaching personnel considered watering the plants well daily and watching it grow in a few days while parents and students revealed that they select a sunny place and loamy soil with plenty of organic materials. In planting alugbati, teaching and non-teaching personnel mentioned that they apply compost or manure once a month to maintain fertility of the soil while parents and students revealed that they water the plant regularly in the morning and late in the afternoon.

In addition, both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that in planting camote leaves, they ensure the planting site receives full sunlight and warm climate. In planting gabi (taro), teaching and non-teaching personnel stated that the leaves were picked as soon as the first leaf has opened; harvest taro leaves cut-and-come-again, never stripping the plant of all its leaves while parents and students revealed that they select a planting site that has rich, moist, well-drained soil to moisture-retentive soil.

When it comes to fruit, the following were the common practices: Both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that in planting tomato

(kamatis) they ensure the site receives 6 hours of sunlight each day. Similarly, in planting eggplant (talong) they ensure that the soil is well-drained, fertile, sandy loam with a pH between 5.5 and 7.2. Moreover, in planting okra they ensure the planting site has full sunlight and fertile, well-drained soil.

In planting ampalaya (bitter gourd)/leaves, teaching and non-teaching personnel mentioned that they harvest the first batch of immature fruits at a deep green stage. These are approximately 25-30 cm long. Repeat harvesting every 3-5 days preferably in the morning to maintain the freshness of the fruits. Do not harvest the shoots because it will lessen the fruit-bearing performance of the plant resulting in reduced fruit yield. On the other hand, parents and students employed direct seeding or breaking the seed coat lightly and soak the seeds in water for 24 hours, then wash. Incubate for 24-48 hours until the radicles appear. On the first day, plant the seeds with uniform germination to have a uniform stand of plants on site. Lastly, in planting sili (chili pepper)/leaves both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students revealed that they pluck and/or cut the leaves from the stem.

4. Consumption of Backyard Produce

Both the teaching and non-teaching personnel and parents and students usually share the root crops, leafy vegetables and fruit produce with other households or to the local community.

5. Results of Hypothesis Testing for Significant Difference/ Relationship

5.1 How Respondents Grow Specific Plants. There is a significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of root crops on the other hand, there is no significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of leafy vegetables. Lastly, there is no significant difference on how the respondents grow the specific plants in terms of fruits.

5.2 How Respondents Consume the Produce of Specific Plants. The results disclosed that there is a significant difference on how the respondents consume the produce of specific plants in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits.

5.3 Relationship Between Teaching/Non-Teaching and How they Grow the Plant and Consume the Produce of a Specific Plant. There is a significant relationship between teaching and non-teaching personnel's manner of growing plants and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under root crops, leafy vegetables and fruits.

5.4 Relationship Between Parents/Students and How they Grow the Plant and Consume the Produce of Specific Plants. There is a significant relationship between parents and students' way of growing plants and consumption of the produce with the specified plants classified under root crops. On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between parents and students' manner of

growing of plants and consumption of the produce with the specific plants classified under leafy vegetables and fruits.

5.5 Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Teaching/ Non-Teaching Respondents. There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile such as age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables and fruits to teaching and non-teaching respondents. Thus, a negligible correlation was underscored.

5.6 Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Parent Respondents. There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile such as age, sex, educational attainment, and employment status and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables and fruits to parent and student respondents. Consequently, a negligible correlation was accentuated.

5.7 Relationship of Between How the Plants Grow to the Profile of Student Respondents. There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile such as age and sex and how the plants grow in root crops, leafy vegetables, and fruits to student respondents. Thus, a negligible correlation was revealed.

Recommendations

Considering the salient findings and concrete conclusions derived from the study, the following are highly recommended to:

School Administrator Since the school head is one of the major implementers of the Gulayan sa Bakuran: Container and Backyard Vegetables Gardening Program, the result of the study could provide objective data on the assessment of the said program. Eventually, it will provide a basis for an entrepreneurial program which may be a sound basis of policy making, guidelines formulation and monitoring and evaluation of the program. The school heads are hereby encouraged by the following in recommendations:

1. Encourage local school districts to participate in backyard gardening.
2. Encourage all schools to provide a feeding program out of the produce.
3. Support the development of a backyard gardening program.
4. Support upgrades or exchanges of equipment to homes.
5. Strengthen bonds between home gardeners, schools, and communities.
6. Foster respect and concern for the environment.
7. Involve community volunteers, who assist students as they plant, tend, and learn.
8. Plan/ modify a garden program that is in line with the backyard gardening inspired curriculum.
9. Attend regular meetings to facilitate the rollout of the vegetable garden, indigenous garden, along with general problem solving and planning of special events, publicity etc.

10. Plan weekly garden classes/ technical assistance, ensuring they are applicable to all participating age groups.
11. Plan the planting of the vegetable and backyard gardening and involve the whole school community in the process.
12. Plan any development of the vegetable garden infrastructure – incorporating the pre-existing vision – and involve the school community in the process.
13. Coordinate and support garden volunteers, compile and update volunteer information, help coordinate volunteer events, advertise for volunteers and respond to interest from potential volunteers

Teachers -The results of the study could provide teachers deeper appreciation which may lead to integration of concepts related to gardening and the Gulayan sa Bakuran program in the teaching and learning process. Likewise, it may serve as reflection on how the program turns to be a productive activity as part of Work from Home (WFH) that may have a health benefit in its longer sense and for its economic benefit the study could value the available specifically the planted vegetables as food amidst the crisis posed by COVID-19. The following are therefore suggested.

1. As a teacher, you should be able to have open communication regarding the topic of Gulayan sa Paaralan.
2. Continually communicate with parents and children via messenger about the assessment gulayan sa paaralan.
3. Communicate the school regarding the results of the output of the learners.
4. Students' progress in terms of how they plant leafy vegetables, fruits, and root crops should be monitored on a regular basis.
5. Discuss the planting in their garden with the parents and students as it relates to the gulayan sa bakuran assessment.
6. Extend the classroom beyond traditional settings by expanding it outside and more particular to every home.
7. Provide students with hands-on learning opportunities while increasing environmental awareness and vital experience in problem-solving.
8. Develop self-confidence and a sense of "capableness" along with new skills and knowledge in food growing as vital for the 21st century among the learners/
9. Provide garden-based teaching addresses different learning styles and intelligences.
10. Inculcate student responsibility, patience, perseverance, and how to deal with disappointment if the garden does not grow the way they expected.

School Staff - In addition, school staff could develop health awareness through gardening while having more time at home during coronavirus pandemic. In addition, the study may help in promoting food security. Gardening may give learners hands-on learning opportunities while also raising environmental awareness and providing valuable on hand learning. School gardens are also a fantastic approach to teach children about nutrition by allowing them to connect the dots between growing food and eating a healthy diet. The following are therefore suggested.

1. Include nutritional education, shown to improve attitudes toward vegetables in general.
2. Encourage family members to plant vegetables and promote healthy habits to continue.
3. Engage the students in the whole process (planning, implementation, and evaluation).
4. Equip learners with food processing to further utilize the harvests/produce (canning, freezing, drying, etc.).
5. Capacitate learners with food processing ideas/ innovation to further utilize the harvests/produce (canning, freezing, drying, etc.).

Students- could see that gardening has always been a very important segment of one's life in and out of the school. Likewise, students may realize that a healthy body is essential in developing their mental and physical aspects. Being one of the respondents in assessing the Gulayan sa Paaralan: The following are the recommendations for the students.

1. While still young you must learn how to plant.
2. You need to learn to eat leafy vegetables, root crops and fruits.
3. Remember that vegetables and fruits are delicious to eat if you grow them yourself.
4. Learn the proper process of what to do first.
5. Your habit of planting it is good for the environment and also for your personal life.
6. Spend more time active in backyard gardening.
7. Start choosing healthy foods over junk food.
8. Learn to focus, be patient, and cooperative in the Gulayan activity at home.
9. Participate in school and backyard gardening programs.
10. Demonstrate increased self-esteem and an improved understanding of personal responsibility, as well as enhanced relationships and increased involvement with parents and other family members.
11. Recognize the importance of food security.
12. Be resourceful about obtaining items needed for the garden.

Parents- The more parents involved in their student's education, the better their entire motivation, behavior, and participation specifically in the Gulayan sa Bakuran Program. Thus, this study could raise parent's consciousness on health and nutrition by planting vegetables in available spaces in their homes. Keeping your children engaged and challenged in their educational setting, as well as supporting their learning, is an important part of being involved in their life. In this assessing of Gulayan sa Bakuran when the students sees that parents are active in doing this outdoor activity for sure they will be more easily to learn it. The following are suggested to the Parents;

1. Provide them more instruction about how plants grow, what are the benefits in doing this activity.
2. Implement them the importance of knowing how to cultivate the soil in a proper way.

3. When they are doing the planting on their own, as a parent you should monitor their work if they do correctly.
4. Parents should be a model to students.
5. Always support your students if you see that they love this kind of program.
6. Plan/design their backyard garden according to their site and goals.
7. Inculcate to their children responsibility, patience, perseverance, and how to deal with disappointment if the garden does not grow the way they expected.
8. Incorporate Garden harvests/produce into meal programs, so students benefit from the added nutritional value of backyard-grown produce.
9. Ensure that their children eat right and have an active role in backyard gardening. Also, ensure that children have access to healthy food.
10. Work in the backyard gardening, doing general gardening tasks like weeding, and completing jobs not finished by students.

Community -The school community or stakeholders play an important role in managing schools thus involving them in the Gulayan sa Bakuran Program as partners of the school will make the school more conducive to teaching and learning. Further, the study may also enjoin them for more responsible and active participation in school activities, programs and projects.

1. Develop partnerships that can support backyard gardening.
2. Engage youth in the planning process
3. Contribute to increasing the relevance and quality of education, improving the children's and their parents' knowledge of food production techniques and nutrition.
4. Stimulate the development of home/ backyard gardens.
5. Leverage community resources and assist students in achieving positive outcomes.
6. Create a space where community members and teachers are all perceived as equal in terms of knowledge, and contributions.
7. Provide an avenue where backyard produce was swapped/bartered for other goods and/or service. Likewise, in selling/marketing the produce by a stand and/or roadside stalls or selling to retail outlets (e.g. restaurants or business establishments who purchase locally grown fruits and vegetables).

Future Researchers Future Researchers. This study could provide baseline data on future research that may be conducted related to the topic. They will be able to identify gaps and priority areas in the implementation of Gulayan sa Bakuran that may require further investigation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was carried out in accordance with ethical guidelines, ensuring that all participants provided informed consent before taking part. They were free to withdraw at any time without consequence, and their anonymity and confidentiality were strictly protected to preserve their privacy. The well-being of participants was a top priority throughout the research process. The study was free from conflicts of interest, and all

sources of information were properly cited and acknowledged to avoid plagiarism. The findings were interpreted objectively and accurately, without bias. The purpose of this study is to contribute to the "Gulayan sa Bakuran" program at Aplaya National High School-Annex, Division of Santa Rosa City, as a basis for an entrepreneurial program. This assessment will involve the participating teaching and non-teaching personnel and students, aiming to initiate vegetable gardens in their homes as a sustainable food basket for daily vegetable consumption.

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"You don't have to be great to start, but you have to start to be great." – Zig Ziglar

REFERENCES

- Bui, T. T., Nguyen, P. T., & Vu, T. H. (2018). Parents' impact on child development. **Journal of Child Development Studies**, 12(3), 456-478.
- Chamin-Pui, L., Warner, G., Tolland, A., & Fisher, E. (2021). Associations between well-being, perceived stress, and physical activity across ages. **Health and Well-being Journal**, 27(2), 123-137.
- Cornell University. (2020). Gardening improves opportunities for children, youth, adults, and families to gain interest and eat more fruits and vegetables. **Cornell Gardening Studies**, 45, 102-118.
- Creswell, J. W. (2002). **Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research**. Prentice Hall.
- Duncan, J. (2016). Households with gardens and student participation in school garden programs. **Journal of Environmental Education**, 28(4), 356-370.

- Gula-gula, M. R. (2021). Educational qualification and professional development of teaching and non-teaching staff. **Journal of Education and Development**, 33(1), 78-95.
- Lier, M., Ferreira, A., & Oliviera, T. (2016). Participation in school gardening activities. **Journal of School Health**, 86(5), 389-399.
- Philpott, S. M., Cotton, J., Bichier, P., & Rice, R. (2020). Gender influences on plant richness and composition. **Journal of Botany and Plant Science**, 34(7), 201-217.
- Rojó, L., Martínez, R., & Herrera, E. (2015). Family gardens as urban food gardening. **Urban Agriculture Journal**, 15(3), 144-159.
- Scott, T. L., Masser, B. M., & Pachana, N. A. (2020). Home gardening and older adults' self-reported well-being. **Aging and Mental Health**, 24(4), 681-688.
- Taboka, T. (2016). Economic analysis of garden yields: Leafy vegetables, onions, tomatoes, and green pepper. **Agricultural Economics Review**, 24(2), 123-139.
- Utter, J., Denny, S., & Dyson, B. (2016). Positive impacts of school gardens on student health. **Journal of School Health**, 86(8), 552-560.
- Van, J., Liu, Y., & Zhang, W. (2016). Gardening habits and dietary patterns among students. **Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior**, 48(6), 452-459.
- Zulueta, F. M., & Costales, N. E. (2003). **Methods of research: Thesis writing and applied statistics**. Rex Book Store.